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Guest Editor in Chief
Dr. Avanish Kumar Upadhyay

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A Message from the Editor-in-Chief/Editors

It given me a great feeling of pleasure to release the special issue of International Research Journal '**Shodh Manthan**'. It is great matter of pride any happiness that eminent researchers, scholars, professionals and academicians have contributed their papers with care and sincerity for success this special issue.

Research orientation has gained a momentum for aspiring educationist and professionals. New dimension have been explored in the field of different disciplines of knowledge. Another important dimension has reached to education field – the experiment of various disciplines all together or experimenting on a field using different sciences. We welcome the coming of rain with a new zest as new possibilities are no more a word out of a changing mind sets ready to evolve. Earlier study of discipline was done in a monotonous way but now the scenario has changed and more new researches are coming up. Needless to say any papers that your wish to submit, either individually or collaboratively are much appreciated and will make a substantial contribution to the development and success of journal.

The theme of journal is multi-disciplinary in nature. They have explored the theme from different point of views. Very large numbers of papers were received. After screening, sufficient number of papers is published in the journal. Papers from research scholars are also given space in the journal. Though they are not well knitted, yet in order to motivate them, their papers are included.

Present journal '**Shodhmanthan**' is an outcome of research papers on the theme '**Global Research in Dynamic World: Issues and Challenges**'. The theme attracted the attention of intelligentsia and academia and they shared their valued views and opinions on the topic in such a grave and sincere manner thoughts an alluring share of journal. In the successful completion of Journal, we are first brimming with deep love and adoration to the divinity responsible for each and every act and decision. We would like to place on record my deep sense of appreciation and thanks to the research scholars and academicians for their efforts in exploring new vistas of research in diverse disciplines and making their articles original and weighty. We express our heart-felt gratitude to Principal, R.H.G.P.G.C.Kashipur standing with us at every juncture from beginning to completion of the journal. We are greatly obliged to each and every person for extending his helping hands. We have deep credence in our readership who would surely not hesitate in expressing their critical opinion for the betterment of present journal and our future endeavors.

Profound Regards,

Dr. Avanish Kumar Upadhyay

Dr.Amit Agrawal

Dr. Sanjay Kumar

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ETHICAL ISSUES IN SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH

Neha Tripathee

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Science, as we all know, has been boon for mankind in all the possible dimensions of life but at the same time, it can play the role of the demon if used in a wrong way. This is why there is a need for having some morals or ethics in all the field of research. Various professions have been given various oaths either officially or casually. But it has found a very important place in professions like, doctors are given the Hippocratic oaths of medics. They are made to realize the importance of their profession of saving lives. They swear to respect the hard-won scientific knowledge of other physicians and also to share own knowledge for benefitting mankind. Along with this, they are also sworn to keep the “patients life” ahead of all other issues. In united states engineers have to take an oath to abide by the “code of ethics” called “the obligation of an engineer”. They pledge to practice integrity and fair dealing. Engineers have a *ring ceremony* to mark this event. Attorney journal have oath to support the constitution of united states and faithfully discharge of duties. In the same way other professions also may have different oaths or code of ethics.

Are the ethics still alive?

Although, time to time questions have been raised on the validity and authority of these oaths. Experts suspect whether without any obligation and compulsions these oaths have any meaning? But the supporters say that even if not having any legal clout these give a moral compass which guides the practitioner throughout their careers.

Jefferey Kovak, the author of the book *The Ethical Chemist : Professionalism and ethics in science*, have further raised the question on the authority of license to practice scientific research.

In the same way, if we talk about following the code of ethics in publications, we see very few of a whole lot of publications are actually checking the reproducibility of work which is a must for scientific works. Papers need to be checked for plagiarism with advanced software, many times wrong or manipulated data is being used, the source paper or work is not acknowledged. This is even smaller; many scientific works are not even checked for their possible futuristic misuses.

According to the Wikipedia definition, the violation of the standard codes of scholarly conducts and unethical writings in professional scientific research are known as “Scientific misconduct”.

Does everyone understand own responsibility?

Sometimes the reason behind these misconducts may be the ignorance towards their impact or the code of ethics. But in some other incidents, it was all intentional. Few examples of scientific misconducts can be viewed in the following examples-

- Jan Henrik Schon a postdoc at Bell Labs in new jersey, working in the field of superconductivity and molecular electronics(nanoelectronics) could be merited with a noble prize if not found untrue.it was reported that 3 of his unrelated papers had identical graphs including papers in *Science* and *Nature* like well-known and reputed magazines.
- In another case the element with atomic number 118 was reported to be discovered at Lawrence Berkley National Laboratory from Victor Ninov’s computer-aided processing of raw data from cyclotron experiment. At that time no one else in Berkley National Laboratory knew the proper applications of the computer program for data processing. Later on after many years of publication of the report, one of the colleague of Ninov learned the computer program and tried to replicate the results, but he could not. By the help of the computer log file, it was found that data was cut and pasted, numerical values were manipulated.
- The biggest case of scientific misconduct reported so far has been by Claudio Airoidi and Jesus Lima Guerra from Brazil.

- Research by Henk Buck from Eindhoven University of technology in the Netherlands to discover a potential method to inhibit HIV-1 replication was also found to be wrong.
- Bharat Aggarwal, at University of Texas , in the Department of Cancer Research, working on Curcumin for cancer treatment was also reported to commit fraud.
- Scientist from Harvard University working on “Endogenous cardiac stem cell “were reported to present the false data in 2014.
- Alias AlSabati was found the culprit of plagiarism in around 60 of his papers on cancer research.
- The Chemistry professor Platinum Chiranjeevi from Shri Venkateshwara University in Andhra Pradesh was also reported to have plagiarism in more than 70 articles in national and international journals.
- Ms HarukoObokata of Riken,a renowned research organisation in Japan, announced about her achievement to convert a normal adult cell into the totipotent stem cell by a specific kind of process known as STAP (Stimulus triggered acquisition of pluripotency).This work was supposed to further enhance the work of Shinya Yamanaka ,the noble laureate,in the field of regenerative medicines.

But just few months later, the work of Ms Haruko was found to violate the code of scientific conduct. This led her supervisor,a respected and renowned Scientist to be ashamed and hang himself.

In a survey in 2018, 71 % of biomedical academics in Belgium admitted to at least one case of scientific misconduct.

But the question arises whether the scientists or authors only are responsible for such incidents. Are the publishers or firm and other supporting agencies have no role to play in this regard? The answer is” No”. As had the reproductivity of the results given by them been checked before publishing, or the firms could appoint someone to do the experiment once more in the laboratory, the chances of such misconduct could be reduced.

if the plagiarism had been checked before publishing such misconduct could be avoided. But many times, the author claims himself to be innocent or the sufferer. Many times, they claim the ignorance about ethical points.

Keeping these points in view there are many institutions, all around the world ,working in this field. They are conducting various workshops, seminars and also many online classes or modules to create and spread awareness in this regard.

But what about the misconduct after the publication of genuine or actual works. Various examples have been reported, where the product of the experiment has been very wrongly used. For example-

- Dynamite which was earlier prepared by mixing silica with volatile nitroglycerine, for blasting the rocks needed for construction of buildings, bridges, etc. Later on, became a weapon of mass destruction.
- Poly-Chlorinated biphenyls(PCB)is another example. It was prepared to be used in electrical wirings and many other appliances due to being stable towards heat and insulating properties. But, later on, it was found that it is turning out to be carcinogenic. These are non-biodegradable and therefore much more hazardous.
- In the same way, the nuclear fusion and fission reactions could so dangerous that, a little of there misuse can put an end to the whole life on earth.
- Chlorine which was most commonly used for water treatment and killing of germs and bacteria in water has become a tool for mass destruction.
- All the polymers of hydrocarbons which were prepared to produce cookware, or plastic items, bags, etc have now been found the biggest threat to the environment and sea life due to being non- biodegradable.

There are several such examples where the inventor does not hold a direct responsibility in the non-constructive use of their inventions.

But either intentionally or innocently done this misconduct proves to be really dangerous for all the scientific fraternity as well as the research aptitudes.

On one side it disappoints the honest workers, on the other hand it leads to the waste of public resources spent on the reproduction of these works.

Along with this, people lose their faith on advanced scientific researches. For example, in 1998 the parents of America and Britain decided their children not to be given vaccines of measles-mumps-rubella, as one of the scientific research (which was later on proved to be wrong) declared the spread of autism by these vaccines.

This resulted in a high increase in the number of children caught with the above-mentioned diseases in the decades. Even after the retraction of the paper opposing the vaccination, people could not firmly believe in the process of immunisation and even now some activists oppose vaccination in fear of it spreading autism.

Thus, it becomes more and more important for a scientist to think twice or thrice about the possible outcomes. Many of the ongoing projects like Human Genome project, Genetic engineering, Cloning, Geoengineering, perfect baby by Crispr (clustered regularly interspaced short palindromic repeats) etc are controversial on ethical ground.

When in 2015, Chinese Scientists used Crispr to edit human embryo in the laboratory, it sparked global opposition and a plea not to play at God.

According to Chinese medical documents posted in November 2018, a team at the Southern University of Science and Technology, in Shenzhen, has been recruiting couples in an effort to create the first gene-edited babies. At that time, it was planned that a gene named CCR5 has to be removed that possibly may produce a bio-technically created baby that was supposed to conquer the diseases like HIV, Cholera and Smallpox.

But still, the actual report of this project has been showing to perform genetic tests on 24 weeks or 6 months features. And further progress has not been disclosed.

Debates are going on at the same issue, all around the world.

Publish or Perish -

Along with these things it also becomes more important to mention that the more obligation and compulsion on scientists or teachers to get their paper published for maintaining their position, is also one of the most important cause behind the misconduct in writing or publishing. Many universities and institutions have directly linked the promotion of the teacher or scientists with their number of published papers.

So even if a professional does not have a research aptitude, is bound to write a paper and getting it published.

The increasing number of publications also is one of the important cause. These firms have been running on the funds from the fees of printing and publishing the paper. Thus, they also take no pain to recheck and review the work, and just publish it on paying the huge amount of charges.

Thus it once again becomes our moral responsibility to think over it and bring all the researches and publications in the ethical compass.

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THE DECLINING NUMBERS OF DAUGHTERS IN INDIA: PROBLEMS AND SOLUTIONS

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Abstract

For perpetuation of any species, the process of reproduction should be continuous. And, for continuous reproduction there must be a balance between sexes of mating population. In a normal human world, the female population equals or slightly surpasses the number of males. Except in few countries like India, where the gender ratio or the number of females to males is known to be among the most imbalanced in the world. The trend of decline in Child Sex Ratio (CSR), defined as number of girls per 1000 of boys between 0-6 years of age, has been unabated since 1961. The decline from 945 in 1991 to 927 in 2001 and further to 918 in India's 2011 Census is disturbing. These numbers indicate that the 'shining' India is still gender biased. Despite of rise in awareness, advancement of technology and increase in educated individuals; the child sex ratio is in emergency proportion. Many steps have been taken to stop female infanticide, but nothing seems to have changed. Several reasons are attributed to the decline in the number of girls like strong son preference, high maternal mortality, crimes against females and the patriarchal system of the society. The easy availability, affordability and subsequent misuse of prenatal diagnostic tools have also been critical in increasing sex selective elimination of girls leading to low CSR. It is ironical that the creator of life herself is struggling for right to born.

Key Words: CSR, Maternal mortality

Introduction

A United Nations study (John, 2014) has warned about the steadily declining child sex ratio in India. India's declining child sex ratio speaks of a culture in which gender inequality is deeply ingrained. Gender biased sex selection is an expression of the subordinate status of women in society, with far reaching socio-demographic consequences. Sex ratio has always been a matter of concern for India. Despite being one of the fastest growing economies in the world, we are still grappled with the declining Child Sex Ratio (CSR).

The CSR in nature

In the absence of manipulation, the sex ratio at birth is remarkably consistent across human populations, with 105–107 male births for every 100 female births (Hesketh and Xing, 2006). This could be explained on the basis of difference in mass of the sperm carrying X and Y chromosome. The sperm carrying Y chromosome is lighter in mass and hence move faster and reach early to the egg. Although sex ratio at birth favors males, differential gender mortality favors females. Females are more resistant to diseases throughout life and have greater overall longevity. If, they have the same nourishment and health care as males, females have lower mortalities across all age groups.

The problem of declining CSR

The ideal 1:1 sex ratio of human population deviates because of deep-rooted traditional preference to the male child or the son. Son preference is most prevalent in an arc of countries from East Asia through South Asia to the Middle East and North Africa (Arnold, 1987). Sons are preferred because (i) they are considered as wage-earner, especially in agrarian economies (ii) they continue the family line; and (iii) they are generally recipients of heritage. Girls are often looked upon as an economic burden because of the dowry system; after marriage they become members of the husband's family, ceasing to have responsibility for their parents in illness and old age.

Trend of CSR in India

Interestingly, the deterioration in the child sex ratio has occurred in the face of rising living standards and improvements in every other indicator of demographic change and human development -average life expectancy, infant mortality, male and female literacy, fertility rate, and schooling enrollment of children. Table 1 shows the trend